

JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

ISSN : 3122-0479

DOI – <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18037670>

**Volume 1 No 2 December (2025): Journal of English
Studies**

**A FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF SELECTED REGISTERS IN THE NIGERIAN STOCK
EXCHANGE DISCOURSE**

<https://joesfudutsinma.com.ng/joes/index.php/one/article/view/32>

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Abstract

English for specific purposes (ESP) has become the mainstay of linguistic investigations that have identified and categorised linguistic registers peculiar to fields such as law, medicine, journalism, religion and the like. Such studies have however not adequately accounted for language forms in the stock exchange market of Nigeria. This study, thus, investigates language forms and the functions they serve in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) market using Halliday's context of situation within Systemic Functional Linguistics. Data was obtained through exchanges on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange and downloaded from their website. The study identified specific lexical and linguistic expressions that are peculiar and unique to the NSE such as: stocks, stockbrokers, share-holders, agents; ask or offer, bulls, bears, assets, assignment, bid, cash, Day Order, defensive-stock, delivery, Delta, and demand which assume different meanings in their contextual usage in the NSE than they are known for in their conventional usage. The study identifies that the English language used on the floor of the NSE is a patterned activity with a unique structure that is peculiar and with particular meanings that are context-dependent. This qualifies the NSE to a register that is unique to it, as all other fields and understanding same, is necessary for understanding issues of the Stock Exchange.

Keywords: Register, Systemic linguistics, Stocks, Discourse.

Introduction

The Stock Exchange is a facility where shares in companies are bought and sold; securities, such as shares of stock and bonds; as well as other financial instruments (Oxford Learner's Dictionary, 5th edition). The first Stock Exchange was opened in Amsterdam, in 1602. Today, the three biggest stocks are the New York, London and Tokyo stocks. The Nigeria Stock Exchange (henceforth, NSE) was established in 1960 as the Lagos Stock Exchange (LSE), but in 1970 its name was changed to Nigerian Stock Exchange with about 169 listed companies. With a total

capitalization of over ₦13 trillion as at May 31, 2018, the NSE is indeed, the bulwark of Africa's largest economy, growth and development (Accessed online at www.nse.org.ng)

Statement of the problem

Extant studies such as Hobsbaum, (1970 and Hutchinson and Waters 1987) have revealed so much on the registers of law, religion, politics, education, sports, journalism and so many others but very little is said or known on the language of use on the floor of the Stock Exchanges. This study, thus, investigates the varieties of language that obtains on the floor of the Nigeria Stock Exchange in order to determine the language form(s) and the function(s) they serve in the context of use.

Methodology and Theoretical Framework

The corpus of the data used in this study was downloaded online on the website of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). Five proceedings of the Stock Exchange (NSE) were downloaded between November 2019 and February, 2020 and subjected to a functional linguistic analysis in order to determine the language forms and functions that obtain in the context of the NSE. The study is undergirded by Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics particularly aspects that relate to context of situation that shows how language functions within particular backgrounds.

Overview of Related Literature

Here, concepts that are relevant to this study are reviewed and discussed.

Variety of English on the floor of the Nigeria Stock Exchange

At the centre of any discussion in every human society lies language. Little wonder it is said that, "language is by a long way, the most efficacious method we have of recalling, judging and conveying experience" (Hobsbaum, 1970: xiv). Hutchinson and Waters (1987) say that "the language we speak and write varies considerably; and in a number of different ways, from one context to another... this gave rise to the view that there are important differences between, say, the English of commerce and that of engineering" (7). Mabel Idebe and Isaac Eyi Ngulube examined Politics and Politicking Registers in Nigerian Campaigns. On his part, Charles Ferguson investigated Dialect, Register and Genre as he looked at Working Assumptions about

Conventionalisation, in D. Biber and E. Finegan (eds), *Sociolinguistics Perspectives and Register*. (1994:15-30). Conversely, Glendinging and Holmstrom (1987) examined *English in Medicine* to determine its peculiarities.

Going by the foregoing results, one observes that there has been wide research into the nature of particular varieties of English like scientific and technical English; or language of law, medicine, advertisement etc. All these studies focus on how language application in special fields operate. This presupposition is based on the basic principle that the English of, say, Electrical Engineering constituted a specific register different from that of Biology or of General English. However, it was found that register analysis did not reveal remarkable distinction in the grammar of science; it was observed that English language use varies from the pronounced and preferred use of particular English language forms like the present simple tense, the passive and nominal compounds depending on the field or discipline of language users.

But the constant and institutionalized use of some lexical and grammatical forms that serve to typify such language varieties (e.g. Medicine, law etc.) make it possible for them to be identified and classed as particular dialects or registers. In fact, Widdowson's (2004) observation could be proper in the identification of registers that describe special variety. ... "lexical and grammatical co-occurrences of collocation and colligation ... can be seen as indicators and makers in that they reveal patterns of usage which, in correlation with kinds of speakers of settings of use, can serve to typify different varieties as dialects or registers" (63).

The lexical and grammatical co-occurrences of collocation; and their correlational usage by stock-exchange managers, brokers and practitioners within the context and settings of use, no doubt, typify and identify the variety of English used on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange. It is a variety of English used for specific purposes. It is a variety of English that clearly identifies the unique "markers of language structure and language use, different from the language of other communication situations" (Ferguson, 1994:20). It is in the light of the specialized usage of; and or application of such lexical and grammatical items on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange that

this study seeks to explore. In line with this, is our aim of comparing how lexical and grammatical features of general English become linguistic tools (devices) in a uniquely different use on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

The Choice of the Nigerian Stock Exchange

Language is no longer studied outside the user of language because it (language), in its multitudinous functions could achieve communicative needs of man; positively or negatively; as in giving commands, abusing, persuading, confusing etc. (Kparevzua 2009). Little wonder then as corroborated in the biblical story in Genesis 11:1-9 that it was the confusion in man's language that stopped the building of the Tower of Babel to the heavens. This means that man needs to know and understand the language that defines a profession or trade in which one shares knowledge or experience of, or has interest on. Without the knowledge of the language in professions like law, medicine or even Stock Exchange, many people outside these specialized linguistic professional groups would stand short changed for being ignorant of the discussions. For instance, Gibbons (2006) writes that the legal jargon has the inherent features of finding one guilty or innocent through language manipulation; not necessarily from verifiable facts. In Nigeria, indeed other parts of the world, many people even among the educated, do not consciously take time to study the peculiarities of the type of language forms in their chosen endeavours. Hence, not everyone has the privilege to access education that could put one in a better stance to understand financial events and situations or contextual financial matters that form discussions on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, hence the need for this study. The fact is that being "educated" in appropriate knowledge of letters is not the same thing with being educated in financial issues that need knowledge of specific language genre for that specific purpose. Olatunji (2007) notes that education is not the same as financial intelligence. For education to be impactful to an individual, one needs to understand the language which is used in particular given contexts to acquire such education. But for language to be classified as language at all, it must also create room for there to

be communication from individual to individual. Thus, any language that communicates must also necessarily have meaning as well. This is why a study of language in any one area, say, the Nigeria Stock Exchange, must be a study that derives justification from its being meaningful to its users (and the general participants) in the overall need for human communication. Furthermore, it must be a language, no matter its specialty, applied in the context of its simplicity towards not just understanding its codes, lexis and grammar, but in positively meeting the need to know it through disambiguation and simplification. Or how can one be seriously engaged in the business of the Nigeria Stock Exchange or any of such “restricted” registers without the opportunity to understand the language in which such business is transacted on daily basis?

It must also be stressed that rules, codes or particular peculiar terms used in any one language are not meaningful in themselves until made meaningful by their application to the contexts to which they are used. Moreover, man is the centre of any communication; and so the peculiar codes that typify Stock Exchange language (or any technical language at that) must take cognizance of all those involved in the business of communication. Crystal (1987), commenting on complaints from the public over doctor-patient communication acknowledges; as some patients did; that “they (doctors; and in our case, operators of the Nigeria Stock Exchange) leave you in the dark too much. If only they (doctors; Stock-Exchange Practitioners) treated you as if you could understand something... I feel better knowing; you always imagine things are worse than they are (182). The clamour to understand the nature of language used in any one profession or special area of study should not be taken for granted because it is in the knowing that one is not left in the dark too much as one is after all part of the whole system of human communication; be it in law, medicine or Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Text or Discourse of Stock Exchange

The Nigerian Stock Exchange uses its peculiar register characterized by choice of particular grammatical and lexical items in particular situations or contexts. Are such linguistic items employed in particular texts or particular discourse? Text is described as “the verbal record

of a communication event” (Brown & Yule 1983). A communication event is not in a vacuum. Its possibility of existence is founded on the linguistic or lexical items used in any given context (situation). A communication event encompasses the context it is situated in. So, the context defines the text that eventually emerges. The text embodies what does not focus on lexical items alone, but the totality of the clauses and sentences used in the “text”. Therefore, “text” and “discourse” are seen as language above the sentence or the clause (Stubbs, 1983). This means that “text” has to do with larger units of language. According to Stubbs, “text” is very short but “discourse” is not that short though both define linguistic unit larger than a sentence. But it is Trudgill (2003) who clearly records that “discourse” deals with linguistic units at levels above the sentence; which to him, means that “discourse” encompasses “text” and “conversation”. And he further records that any “discourse” analysis would also involve an analysis of social human interactions, which also deals with human conversation, a sociolinguistic phenomenon.

Without looking at the erroneous view of a “text” being very short; it could be concluded that both “text” and “discourse” are above mere isolated sentences. Thus, both are referring to units of language larger than the sentence; both are independent linguistic units, which could be analysed on its own linguistic value and contents application.

It is necessary to conclude therefore, that the Nigerian Stock-Exchange operates technical register using grammatical and lexical items within given contexts, in given “texts” or in given written “discourse” for appropriate and effective communication between and within the Nigerian Stock Exchange linguistic community. And “text” in this context could be viewed, not by length or size but by the given circumstances or situations in which linguistic units (larger than sentences or not) are appropriately applied. However, in this presentation; neither “text” nor “discourse” is of relevance since we shall only be focusing on such linguistic devices (words, lexical items) as used to general English application. There is need to reiterate that the study adopts Halliday’s Systemic Functional Linguistics as the theory, especially the aspects that relate to context of situation that show how language functions within particular backgrounds. The data used in this study was

downloaded from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), between 2019 and 2020 with five proceedings of the Stock Exchange (NSE).

Data Analysis

Linguistic devices used in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

Linguistic devices employed to facilitate meaningful communication among practitioners in the Stock Exchange or they (practitioners) and the teeming customers (i.e., brokers and shareholders) are tested on the scale of choice. In some areas of study which language is central to their flow and meaningful development, the linguistic resources that are used in communicative activities are drawn from the language of such practitioners. For instance, the law- “jargon” is familiar to lawyers because it is the language of law, used by lawyers and meant to be understood by lawyers. But the choices made with regards to the linguistic resources available and those in the field of communication may vary from individual to individual. The most important consideration has been the need to know and understand what is communicated even by those considered “unprofessional”. Thus, there is the option of choosing what could best be easily understood for healthy communication or simply making lexical-grammatical choices that could fall within “ambiguity” and “obfuscation”; resulting to choking communication, as it were.

The Nigeria Stock Exchange, like any technical register, makes choices from a pool of grammatical and lexical items of English language, some of which are easily identifiable as belonging to the general English, but which do not provide meanings from their semiotic structures. The structures of the grammatical and lexical items of English used in Stock Exchange vary as their functions also vary from context to context. Therefore, the structure of register of Stock Exchange is also important in the determination of meaning within their use in particular contexts. Adejare (1995) notes that:

If there is no structure, there will exist no range of meaning; and if there exist no range of meaning, there will be nothing from which to make choices which are appropriate for any context.

Choice of words and word groups

The Nigeria Stock Exchange makes choices from some words and word groups which are sometimes simply divulged from the general English in structure and meaning. However, some of these also take similar patterns of general English word or word-group structure but the meaning is not similar to the applicability of their being used in general English environment. This is not surprising because many of such words and word –groups used in the Stock Exchange are made to form a “configuration of semantic resources ... a cluster of associated features having a greater-than-random tendency to occur in the context of the Nigerian Stock Exchange” (Halliday 1988).

Technical vs General English

There are so many of such words and word-groups that it will be impossible to use all of them in this essay. Suffice to say that many of the words or word groups listed here would be such as look similar with their use or applicability in general English but provide meanings peculiar or unique on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Some of the few words or word groups that are listed for our concern here include “agent”; “ask or offer”; “assets”; “assignment”; “bid”; “cash” “Day Order”; “defensive–stock”; “delivery”, “Delta” “demand” bulls, bears and many such-like. Looking at such words (lexical items) and word groups, one could guess the meanings that are embedded in the linguistic structures. The question is whether such words or word groups could be interpreted to generate similar meanings on both sides of the divide: general English usage and usage as on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Let us take a few examples here:

Sample (1) – “Agent”

On the floor of Nigerian Stock Exchange, the item “agent”; used in the context of its application within that register would stand for “A securities firm that acts on behalf of its clients as buyer or seller of a security” (Online <https://www.tmxmoney.com>>glossary).

The word is a noun used in general English to refer to a “person who acts for; or who manages the business affairs of another or others; for e.g. ‘house-agent’ ‘literary-agent’ ” etc. It appears as though this usage (Hornby’s Oxford Advanced Learners’ Dictionary pp.17) is synonymous with the usage of the word in the Stock Exchange communication. But whereas in the contexts of the Stock Exchange, the word defines a “firm” that acts on behalf of its client; in general English (barring the context used) the same word refers to a person who acts from or manages for someone else. In general English also, the same word could mean different things; e.g. “secret-agent” as in person rendering secret-services, or “agent” to stand for substance, or natural phenomenon producing an effect (as in sciences). So although the word; as simple as it appears could seem to share similar meanings both in general usage and on the floor of the Stock Exchange; it is not possible for such a similarity based on the clear distinction between its usage on general terms and its usage on the technical terms. What is, however, important to note is that such a word like many others, use simple normal English structure but generate meaning or denote entities that are purely peculiar in the communicative-space of the English used in the Nigerian Stock Market.

This point can further be stressed using the following:

Sample (2) “Assignment”

Again, this is a familiar word; particularly in the school or academic environment where its application in the context of teacher-student relationship elicits disapproval and anxiety to students. In that context, it stands for assigning something (e.g. work duty) to somebody. For example, a teacher assigns work to be done. But the same word could mean giving something to someone which may be for use, enjoyment or as one’s share. Still, on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange, the same linguistic item stands for a notification to the seller of an option by the clearing corporation; the buyer of the option is enforcing the terms of the option’s contract”.

(<https://www.tmxmoney.com>>glossary)

Sample (3) “Cross”

Again, this is a case of using a familiar word in the general usage of English language; but which word draws meaning peculiar only to Stock-Exchange lexicon. The word “cross” in other meanings outside Stock Exchange could stand for a “mark made by drawing one line across another, thus, x, +” (Hornby, *ibid* 205). We also often hear people talking about “crossing the ‘ts’ and dotting the ‘Is’”. Hornby (*ibid*) also looks at “cross” as “stake or post with another piece of wood across it like T, + or X as used in ancient times for crucifixion”. “The cross” is actually a model of religious emblem which describes one on which Christ (Jesus) died. But the word “cross” could also be a verb-form (not noun-form) which is indicative of movement, like passing from one side to the other side (Hornby, *ibid*). Most users of the word “cross” in semi-literate, and even literate societies in Nigeria, use it colloquially thus, “Don’t cross me”, which is intended to mean “Don’t annoy me”. The word “cross” in colloquial term means “bad tempered; easily or quickly showing anger”, as in, “Don’t be cross with the child for being late” (<https://www.tmxmoney.com>glossary>). In fact, “cross” is used as a form of word to collocate with other words in a compound-structure for diverse meanings. For example, “cross-bar” – bar going across, “cross-beam” placed across, “cross-breed” –animal, plant etc. produced by crossing different kinds, “cross-check”-verify by using a different method etc. There are many of such compound-words preceded by the word “cross” and such compound words fall in different grammatical categories, e.g. nouns; as in “cross-benches”, “cross-bones”-where the head-word is a noun modified by “cross” or adjectives, as in “cross-bred”, “cross-cut”, “cross-country” etc. where the head is adjective. And sometimes the compound word is a verb, transitive or intransitive as in “cross-fertilize”.

But the word “cross” used on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange attracts meaning completely outside the various meanings generated by its usage whether in simple or compound state. “Cross” in NSE terminology defines “a trade that occurs when two accounts within the same participating organization (member) wish to buy and sell the same security at an agreed price and volume (only within current “bid” and “ask” for the stock”.

Sample (4) “Beta”

Technically, this word is a noun that stands for second letter (B.β) of the Greek alphabet (Hornby, *ibid*, 78). However, in the grammar of English, “beta” operates at the dependent-clause structure of the sentence (Σ), the unit higher than the clause. Where a complex sentence operates two elements of structure called alpha (α) which can stand alone as a simple sentence and the optional element called beta (β) which cannot stand alone; for e.g. “When he comes, tell him to eat his lunch”. – Structure is beta (β) and alpha (α) respectively. (Muir, 1972:69). However, on the floor of NSE, the same word defines “a measurement of the relationship between the price of a stock and the movement of the whole market” (online, <https://www.tmxmoney.com>>glossary).

There are therefore many such grammatical and lexical forms that are used in the NSE in uniquely different ways and meanings from their similar usages in ordinary communicative activities in Nigeria. Therefore, such stock, special usages of seemingly simple words or lexical or group of items like: “Better –price-limit-orders”, “Buy-in”, “Bypass-order”, “Day Order”, “Delivery” etc; when used on the floor of NSE could mean exactly what is determined by professional application and contextual necessity.

Sample (5) “Delta”

Look at a word like “Delta” used in the Stock Exchange. In ordinary usage, this word stands to either describe “Greek” letter ‘d’ or “land (with alluvial deposits) within a particular shape” (Hornby, 229). In Nigeria, the word “Delta” brings up the name of one of the States in the South-South region of the country; with large deposits of oil. But NSE uses the similar word to professionally and contextually define a “ratio that measures an option of the price movement compared to the underlying interest’s price movement” (online, <https://www.tmxmoney.com>>glossary). Also, any time one comes across simple words like “demand”, “delist”, and “commission”, “commodities”, “capital”, “cash” etc. one must not simply

conclude their meanings on the fact that such words also apply in marketing or some other commercial disciplines. This is because NSE has its vocabulary and lexicon; and the determination of what, how, why, where or when such language –forms (turned registered -forms) are used to rest not upon their dictionary or normal English usage as to their applicability, professionally or technically and contextually. And the choices made in this respect are not tailored along optionality but professional necessity which also goes to define what meanings to be interpreted from the technical forms.

The NSE as a Register of its own

Crystal (1987) notes the place of language in the daily routine of medical practice “outside the world of the research laboratory and clinic, there exist the daily routine of the medical practice –a communication situation in which a doctor attempts to understand the problems of a patient and the patient’s attempts to understand the doctor’s diagnoses. Language is involved at each point in the medical consultation” (382). This may be applied in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Language is involved at each point in the transactions therein. The question is whether such language as used for NSE between practitioners and perhaps the shareholders or customers is language applied within the realm of the ordinary literate man.

We have seen that even the seemingly simple grammatical and lexical forms of English used on the floor of NSE generate meanings outside the ordinary meanings of such forms. Still, in many other forms, the words are technical forms that require purely technical interpretation, with regards to the operations and practices in the NSE. For example; “Bear Market” is a technical term that stands for “a market in which stock prices are falling.” It is literally-interpreted as “market for bears” (a wild animal) where one walks into and gets a “bear”. Or one can have collocation of words, “Blue-chip-stocks” to define type of “stocks of leading and nationally known companies that offer a record of continuous dividend payments and other strong investment qualities”. A few other technically-interpreted forms could be given in the following examples.

Sample (6) “Board Lot”

This stands for “A standard trading unit as defined in UMIR (Universal Market Integrity Rules). The Board Lot size of a security on Toronto Stock Exchange or TSX Venture depends on the trading price of the security” (online, *ibid*).

Sample (7) “Bonds”

This technically defines “promissory notes issued by a specified amount of interest for specified length of time”.

Sample (8) “Bull Market”

This term is not that there is a special market where one goes to get a “bull” of one’s choice. It is a term in NSE, opposite in meaning to the term “Bear Market”. Whereas “Bull Market” stands for market in which stocks are rising, “Bear market” stands for market in which stocks are falling. Why one market is named “Bear” and another “Bull” does not concern us but brings to bear on the seemingly simple lexicon used in NSE.

Sample (9) “Cum-Dividend”

“Cum-Dividend – with Rights”. This means that the owner of shares cum-dividend is entitled to an upcoming already-declared dividend. The opposite of this is “Ex-dividend.

Sample (10) “Cum-Rights”

“Cum-Rights – with Rights” - In this term, owners of shares cum-rights are entitled to forthcoming already-declared rights. The opposite of this is “Ex-Rights”.

The Nigerian Stock Exchange also use particular abbreviations (acronyms) which stand for technical terms with particular meanings which are generated by contextually-determined premises. For example: - UMIR - stands for “Universal Market Integrity Rules”, a body of rules that governs and defines standard trading unit (i.e. Board Lot).

BCICAC – This stands for British Columbia International Commercial Arbitration Centre.

This body is an arbitration centre established to resolve business disputes that have not been resolved through normal channels.

BCSC – This stands for British Columbia Securities Commission. It is the provincial government’s agency responsible for administering and enforcing the security Act and the commodity contract Act of British Columbia.

CUSIP – This acronym stands for Committee on Uniform Security Identification Procedures. This body defines “a standard system of securities identification and description; used in electronic processing and recording of securities transactions in North-America”. (Online, *ibid*).

These are a few examples of some acronyms and abbreviations used in Stock Exchange generally, but which also have the functions of they being used for reference towards achieving international best practices in Nigerian Stock Exchange. And from all indications, the Nigerian Stock Exchange exhibits a special lexicon and grammar of English Language which stands it out as using its Register. It is a language that is familiar in the floor of NSE, and practiced by and between interlocutors; within this specialized speech –community. The “linguistic-ideology” that has identified the medical or legal or any other one profession possessing own unique Register; has also made it necessary to believe that the NSE has its own Register. The content words (nouns, verbs, adjectives etc.); the lexical elements, the acronyms, the sentences, the metaphors (bear market etc.) – all are applied consciously within the “linguistic-ideology” or “culture” of the Stock Exchange generally, and the Nigerian Stock Exchange particularly.

The need to know the NSE Jargon

It is believed in some circles that communication that goes on in special areas like law or even NSE is meant to exclude non-practitioners and in that sense, to discourage outsiders from participating in an area of communication that they are not welcome nor encouraged to be in. It is recorded in Johnstone (2002, 2005) that speaking and writing in a legal way or style would help others to identify one as an insider e.g. a legal practitioner; and that would create a meaningful rapport with other insider-practitioners. It can also help “define that situation as a legal one, and it can serve as a move to exclude from participation, people who do not control the register or to put

them in the weaker position” (149). But is this true of the use of language on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange? Perhaps, that may be so, given that NSE also uses a particular Register in its communicative activities. However, there has never been any reason to believe willy-nilly that insiders who use English deliberately exclude others from participating in their official communication.

The work of the language practitioner and researcher does not stop at mere descriptions of how language is used to achieve different lexico-semantic or lexico-grammatical or syntactic, or even pragmatic devices in conveying different meanings (explicitly or implicitly). The language researcher must necessarily try to demystify language-practice in all areas of human communication (medicine, law NSE etc.) which many believe are “no-go-areas” of practice by ordinary language users. If language is primarily created and used for communication in a broad-spectrum, among all who have the need-to-know it, then no one linguistic area should be seen as its own “island” purely for its own “islanders”.

Crystal (1987) is of the opinion that using technical vocabulary (as in NSE) is “... the most precise means of expressing technical and complex ideas ... scientists, doctors, bankers and others (NSE) need their jargon in order to communicate with each other succinctly and unambiguously” (379). However, we believe that human language and communication is not that so structured, and therefore, stands the risk of encountering such issues like “ambiguity” if other people are not allowed the opportunity to speak or use it. For example, a share-holder may feel cheated because he is surrounded by words, phrases, sentences which are merely intimidating than communicative. The relevance of language (in any one area for that matter), is to communicate its meaning.

In fact, Berlo (1960:169) submits that “the concept of meaning is central to communication”. Therefore, if the register of NSE is to make meaning, it must communicate not only to the users- “insiders” but to all of us (customers, share-holders; Stock-speculators etc.) who, I believe, ‘...feel better knowing you always imagine things are worse than they are’ (Crystal,1987).

Conclusion

It is stated that language “is a patterned activity that has structure” (Mur, 2). The English language used on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) is a patterned activity, It also has structure as well. The linguistic structure is observed in the use of particular words, lexical items, abbreviations or acronyms, all of which give expression to particular meanings that are context-dependent. Context-dependent is here measured in our observation that the ordinary use and meanings associated with seemingly normal English words like “book”, “market”, “days”, “assignment”, “assets” etc. convey unique meanings that typify NSE-jargon. Also, we have seen that specialized use is attached to linguistic forms which are technically (professionally) applied just as particular acronyms or abbreviations openly carry the marks of the Stock Exchange Register.

The simplicity of some linguistic forms (words and lexical items) used in NSE could be indicative of the simplicity of language adopted as well. These (simple words) are complemented by the specialized forms, thus, making the overall communication easier, and also enhancing meaningful and freer business and commercial activities. NSE has its unique Register, but there is every need to know, understand and participate in the ways and means of communication on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

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